

This can be explained by considering that the electrostatic repulsion between the primary ligand iminodiacetic acid and the secondary ligand amino acid is more. Iminodiacetic acid bearing two negative charges, therefore, the coordinating tendency of secondary ligand L to combine with [M(IMDA)] decreases significantly. Therefore, mixed ligand formation constant values are significantly lower than $K_{ML_1}^M$ and lower than $K_{ML_2}^{ML_1}$. The higher concentration of L is lowering the values of mixed ligand formation constants K_{MAL}^{MA} . Besides the charge repulsion, other factors may also affect the mixed ligand formation constant K_{MAL}^{MA} .

References

1. B. E. LEACH and R. J. ANGELICI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 907.
2. I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 742.
3. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1975, **75**, 123.
4. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2904.
5. J. D. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 257.
6. I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 469.
7. S. N. DUBBY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 73.
8. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 881.
9. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 941.

Thermodynamic Functions of Biological Molecules. Pyrimidine and some of its Haloderivatives

RAJMUHON N. SINGH, KRISHAN LAL

and

HARI L. BHATNAGAR*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University,
Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 31 October 1985, revised 8 July 1986,
accepted 5 September 1986

VIBRATIONAL analysis of pyrimidines have been studied by various workers¹⁻⁶. Allenstein *et al.*⁷ have studied 2-halopyrimidines and reported all the fundamental frequencies of 2-chloropyrimidine. 2,4,6-Trihalopyrimidines have also been studied by Kizuki *et al.*⁸ and Bailey and Steele^{9,10}. Although the vibrational analysis of these molecules have been studied, the thermodynamic functions of these molecules are not reported. With this end in view, we decided to compute the thermodynamic functions, namely, heat capacity (C_p°), enthalpy function ($H^\circ - E_0^\circ$)/ T , free energy function ($G^\circ - E_0^\circ$)/ T and entropy (S°) for these molecules at a pressure of 1 atm in the temperature range 100–1500 K under the rigid rotor-harmonic oscillator approximation and using the fundamental frequencies available in the literature^{7,9-11}.

Computation of thermodynamic properties: Once the vibrational frequencies of a molecule are known, it is possible to calculate the contribution of the vibrational energy to the total energy possessed by a molecule. In the same way, the rotational energy contribution can be calculated if the moments of inertia of the molecule are known. Thus, the spectroscopically measured frequencies and the moments of inertia are important variables in determining the thermodynamic functions of a molecule.

The total partition function can be expressed as the product of the individual partition functions due to translational, rotational, vibrational and electronic energies. Hence,

$$Q = Q_{\text{trans}} \cdot Q_{\text{rot}} \cdot Q_{\text{vib}} \cdot Q_{\text{elec}} \\ = \sum_i g_i \exp(-\epsilon_i/kT) \quad (1)$$

where, g_i is the statistical weight of the i th energy level¹², k is the Boltzmann constant and T is the absolute temperature. Contribution of each partition function may be evaluated separately and then added to the corresponding thermodynamic function to obtain the total values. The electronic contribution is small and is ignored because ϵ_{elec} is large compared to kT at ordinary temperature. The equations used in computation for various partition functions and their contribution to different thermodynamic parameters are given elsewhere¹³. The standard expressions¹³ as given by Colthup have been used and their contributions to various thermodynamic functions have been calculated at various temperatures. In the present work, computations of the thermodynamic quantities were made on a TDC-316 Computer.

Results and Discussion

The statistical mechanical calculation of the ideal gas thermodynamic properties for a molecule requires the following basic informations: atomic masses, molecular weights, molecular structural parameters, complete fundamental vibrational frequencies (3N-6) and the symmetry number.

The molecular structures of pyrimidine, 2-chloropyrimidine, 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine and 2,4,6-trifluoropyrimidine are taken from literature^{10,14} and are used as such in the calculations. The atomic masses are taken from literature¹⁵: C, 12.011 15; H, 1.007 97; N, 14.006 7; F, 18.998 4; Cl 35.453. All the four molecules have been considered to have C_{2v} symmetry with their external symmetry number σ equal to 2. In the computation of principal moments of inertia I_x , I_y and I_z , all the molecules have been considered as planar and the Z-axis perpendicular to the plane. The fundamental frequencies of pyrimidine, 2-chloropyrimidine, 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine and 2,4,6-trifluoropyrimidine are assigned in references^{7,9-11} to the various modes of vibration. The computed results¹⁶ of the thermodynamic functions, namely, the heat capacity (C_p°) at constant pressure, the enthalpy function ($H^\circ - E_0^\circ$)/ T , the free energy function ($G^\circ - E_0^\circ$)/ T

NOTES

and the entropy (S°) of the four compounds in the temperature range 100–1 500 K are represented by curves in Figs. 1–4. The thermodynamic functions

Fig. 1. Variation of heat capacity with absolute temperature for (○) pyrimidine, (●) 2-chloropyrimidine, (□) 2,4,6-trifluoropyrimidine, and (△) 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine.

Fig. 2. Variation of enthalpy function with absolute temperature for (○) pyrimidine, (●) 2-chloropyrimidine, (□) 2,4,6-trifluoropyrimidine, and (△) 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine.

Fig. 3. Variation of free energy function with absolute temperature for (○) pyrimidine, (●) 2-chloropyrimidine, (□) 2,4,6-trifluoropyrimidine, and (△) 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine.

Fig. 4. Variation of entropy with absolute temperature for (○) pyrimidine, (●) 2-chloropyrimidine, (□) 2,4,6-trifluoropyrimidine, and (△) 2,4,6-trichloropyrimidine.

rise more rapidly in the low temperature range and less rapidly in the high temperature range. The trend of variation of thermodynamic functions with temperature is similar to that reported in literature¹⁷.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.N.S.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. R. H. LARKIN and H. D. STIDHAM, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1973, 29, 781.
2. M. ITO, R. SHIMADA, T. KURAISHI and W. MIZUSHIMA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, 25, 597.
3. R. C. LORD, A. L. MARSTON and F. A. MILLER, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1957, 9, 113.
4. V. I. BEREZIN and S. K. POTAPOV, *Opt. Spectrosc.*, 1966, 18, 22.
5. R. FOGLIZZO and A. NOVAK, *Spectrosc. Lett.*, 1969, 2, 165.
6. J. D. SIMMONS and K. K. INNES, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1964, 13, 435.
7. E. ALLENSTEIN, P. DIEMLE, J. WEIDLIN and W. PODSZUN, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1977, 33, 189.
8. S. KIZUKI, Y. ISHIBASHI, H. SHIMADA and R. SHIMADA *Mem. Fac. Sci. Kyushu Univ., Ser. C*, 1981, 13, 7.
9. R. T. BAILLY and D. STEELE, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1967, 23, 2989.
10. R. T. BAILLY and D. STEELE, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1969, 25, 219.
11. F. M. NEJAD and H. D. STIDHAM, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1975, 31, 1493.
12. W. J. MOORE, "Physical Chemistry", Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, 1962.
13. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1964.
14. F. J. WHEATLEY, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1960, 13, 80.
15. "International Tables for X-ray Crystallography", Vol. III, Kynock Press, Birmingham, 1962.
16. The results in arithmetical numbers can be provided on request to authors.
17. C. L. CHATTERJEE, P. P. GARG and R. M. P. JAISWAL, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1978, 34, 943.

The Kinetic Analysis of Consecutive Irreversible First Order Reaction. Oxidation of Benzhydrazide by Peroxydisulphate

M. B. HOGALE*, M. H. JAGDALE and B. P. NIKAM
Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University,
Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 4 July 1985, revised 26 May 1986,
accepted 5 September 1986

STUDIES on consecutive reactions, including the oxidation by peroxydisulphate¹ are rather limited. Jagdale and Kadam² investigated the silver(I) catalysed oxidation of succinimide by peroxydisulphate and interpreted the results in terms of consecutive reactions. This communication reports the oxidation of benzhydrazide by peroxydisulphate along with a proposed mechanism.

Experimental

Potassium peroxydisulphate (A.R.), benzhydrazide (B.D.H.), silver nitrate (AnalaR) and other chemicals used were of either E. Merck or B.D.H.

All the solutions were prepared in distilled water. The reaction was carried out in thermostated water-bath at 35° (±0.1°) for 240 min. The kinetics were followed by estimating the remaining peroxydisulphate by the method of Szabo *et al.*³ further modified by Khulbe and Srivastva⁴.

Results

The concentrations of benzhydrazide, benzoyldiimide and nitrogen (A, B and C, respectively) formed at any time *t* can be calculated readily by applying the method of Esson⁵. A series of first order reactions can be fitted by plotting concentrations of A, B, C against time (Fig. 1) from the curve of concentration of A against time; k_1 , the rate constant for oxidation of benzhydrazide into benzoyldiimide was found to be $1.91 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The equations for concentrations of A, B and C can be put in simple form by introducing dimensionless parameters⁶ such as α , β , γ , τ and K . Thus α , β and γ were essentially concentrations relative to the initial value A_0 and can vary in the range 0–1 as shown in Table 1. The concentrations of intermediate B as measured by β passes through a

Fig. 1. Plot of concentration of A, B and C against time: (A) benzhydrazide, (B) benzoyldiimide, and (C) nitrogen.

maximum value which depends on K , the relative value of the rate constant. The maximum value of τ is 2.23, β (max)=0.72 and B (max)=7.01 ml for benzoyldiimide. The induction period for benzoyldiimide is 200 min.

Swain's time-ratio method⁷ has been used for accurate determination of the rate constants for